

Spectral line systematics. Extension of the Bohr and Rydberg formulas to include additional atomic energy.

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ABSTRACT

The fundamental particle, the electron, is subject to various theories such as electrodynamics, quantum mechanics, and special relativity.¹

These theories are not mutually exclusive, but complement and verify each other's predictions. The Bohr, Balmer and Rydberg models popular at the turn of the 20th century have been largely replaced by quantum methods, such as the Schrödinger or Dirac equations.

Bohr's formula does not take into account phenomena such as fine structure or more advanced quantum effects. Moreover, the differences between the theoretical results obtained on its basis and the empirical results are significant.

In this paper I will show that these differences do not result solely from quantum effects, but from another, as yet undescribed cause. Importantly, these discrepancies are several orders of magnitude larger than could result from quantum effects, and they concern only selected combinations of orbit numbers.

In other cases, such errors do not occur. For this reason, some emission energy values have been used in the past to precisely define physical constants, while other emission cases do not obey these rules.

The differences in the measured photon energy compared to the energy calculated using Bohr's formula are not inaccuracies or random corrections, but are system differences. They are precisely assigned to the numbers of the initial and final orbits involved in the jump, and depend on the sum of values that I have called "Orbit Markers".

To precisely describe the marker values, I used a new wave unit in my work, which I called the "energy unit" and in this unit, the marker values are integers or quotients of integers. They therefore describe the orbit energies and the electron jump energies between orbits in a lossless way, without using rounding.

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This unit was created during the analysis of wavelengths of hydrogen spectral lines, when it turned out that the frequencies of all studied hydrogen emission waves are harmonics of a certain wave λ_0 and can be described by a new wave unit in natural numbers. Unlike the previous wave number (cm^{-1}), which describes wavelengths with irrational numbers, this number informs about the number of full sinusoidal periods contained in one period of the wave λ_0 . This allows to describe the parameters of spectral lines with full accuracy, without rounding.

As a result of this algorithm, it was possible to calculate with full accuracy the value of the basic energy of the hydrogen electron E_0 , as well as the energies of all orbits of the excited atom and the balance of electron jump energy without losses, in unrounded numbers.

Entry.

The postulate of this work is that the amplitude of each photon emission wave is a constant value, so to maintain the proportionality of energy and the number of periods, it should be stated that:

The energy of a quantum is proportional to the frequency of the radiation

$$E = h \cdot \nu^2 \quad (0,1)$$

where E - photon energy, h is Planck's constant; ν is the emission wave frequency.

The second postulate is that the portions of energy emitted by the atom take place in full periods of the sinusoid, always from the zero point (node) to the next n-th node, different for each emission wavelength.

Below is the logical diagram of converting the energy difference of orbits into a sine wave:

Figure 1 : Logical diagram of the electron energy loss by emitting full periods of a sine wave.

If for the blue wave graph λ_0 we can write that:

$$E_0 = h \cdot \nu_0 \quad (0.3)$$

²Planck's formula (1900)

then for subsequent harmonics n of this wave it is true:

$$n * E_0 = h * (n * \nu_0) \quad (0.4)$$

Since n is the number of periods of the sine wave per wavelength λ_0 , this formula also shows that the energy of one full sinusoidal period for a wave of any frequency $n * \nu_0$ is constant and equal to the energy E_0 .

Chapter 1: We are looking for a wavelength λ_0 that is a common multiple of the hydrogen emission wavelengths being studied .

The hydrogen emission waves from the Lyman, Balmer, Paschen and Brackett series were selected for the study³, i.e. the pairs $\{n = 1, m = 2\}$, $\{n = 1, m = 3\}$, $\{n = 1, m = 4\}$, $\{n = 1, m = 5\}$, $\{n = 1, m = 6\}$, $\{n = 1, m = 7\}$, $\{n = 2, m = 3\}$, $\{n = 2, m = 4\}$, $\{n = 2, m = 5\}$, $\{n = 2, m = 6\}$, $\{n = 2, m = 7\}$, $\{n = 3, m = 4\}$, $\{n = 3, m = 5\}$, $\{n = 3, m = 6\}$, $\{n = 3, m = 7\}$, $\{n = 4, m = 5\}$, $\{n = 4, m = 6\}$, $\{n = 4, m = 7\}$ for the transition from orbit m to n .

Using the Rydberg formula for photon energy:

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_{vac}} = R_H \left(\frac{1}{n_1^2} - \frac{1}{n_2^2} \right), \quad (1,1)$$

gdzie:

λ_{vac} – długość fali w próżni światła emitowanego przez atom,

R_H – stała Rydberga dla wodoru,

n_1 i n_2 – liczby całkowite, $n_1 < n_2$.

Rydberg constant for the hydrogen atom $R = 1.09677 \cdot 10^7 \text{ m}^{-1}$ 4

We calculate the wavelengths λ_{and} for the Lyman, Balmer, Paschen and Brackett lines: 93.02519137 ; 93.7303386 ; 94.92366467 ; 97.20183262 ; 102.5175578 ; 121.5022908 ; 396.9074832 ; 410.0702314 ; 433.9367528 ; 486.0091631 ; 656.1123702 ; 1004.672067 ; 1093.520617 ; 1281.469473 ; 1874.606772 ; 2164.949908 ; 2624.449481 ; 4050.076359 [nm].
(1,2)

The sought value of λ_0 will be the smallest integral multiple of all wavelengths tested simultaneously, but each length λ_{and} with a different multiplicity.

Taking as a basis the highest number λ_{max} (4050.076359) from the set (1,2) and subsequent multiples $k * \lambda_{max}$, we examine the quotient of this number by the subsequent examined lengths λ_{and} , counting the sum of deviations of these numbers from an integer, we look for the sum of remainders close to zero.

$$f(k) = \sum_{i=1}^{5000} | \lambda_{max} * k / \lambda_i - \text{INTEGER}(\lambda_{max} * k / \lambda_i) | \quad (1.3)$$

³<https://www.britannica.com/science/spectral-line-series#ref225383>

⁴https://lex.dk/Rydbergs_konstant

(1,4)

Figure 2. The graph of the function $f(k)$ shows the lowest value of the residuals at point $k_{\min} = 3969$

Knowing k_{\min} we calculate the value of λ_0 as:

$$\lambda_0 = k_{\min} * \lambda_{\max} = 3969 * 4050.076359 \text{ [nm]} = 16074753.06937570 \text{ [nm]} \quad (1.5)$$

To verify the calculations, we must confirm that the wavelength λ_0 is an integral multiple of all waves tested simultaneously:

16074753,06937570	:	93,02519137	=	172800,00
16074753,06937570	:	93,7303386	=	171500,00
16074753,06937570	:	94,92366467	=	169344,00
16074753,06937570	:	97,20183262	=	165375,00
16074753,06937570	:	102,5175578	=	156800,00
16074753,06937570	:	121,5022908	=	132300,00
16074753,06937570	:	396,9074832	=	40500,00
16074753,06937570	:	410,0702314	=	39200,00
16074753,06937570	:	433,9367528	=	37044,00
16074753,06937570	:	486,0091631	=	33075,00
16074753,06937570	:	656,1123702	=	24500,00
16074753,06937570	:	1004,672067	=	16000,00
16074753,06937570	:	1093,520617	=	14700,00
16074753,06937570	:	1281,469473	=	12544,00
16074753,06937570	:	1874,606772	=	8575,00
16074753,06937570	:	2164,949908	=	7425,00
16074753,06937570	:	2624,449481	=	6125,00
16074753,06937570	:	4050,076359	=	3969,00

Figure 3 : Calculation of harmonic numbers [Hn] of the tested waves relative to the wave $\lambda_0 = 16074753.06937570 \text{ [nm]}$

However, counting the wavelengths λ and Bohr's formula we get:

$$\lambda = \frac{hc}{13.6 \text{ eV} \left(\frac{1}{n_1^2} - \frac{1}{n_2^2} \right)}. \quad (1,5)$$

where c - speed of light = 299792458 m/s

h - Planck's constant = $4.135667696 * 10^{-15} \text{ eV*s}$,

This way we obtain slightly different energy values of the spectral lines studied:

93.064119514 ; 93.769561819 ; 94.963387259 ; 97.242508553 ; 102.560458240 ; 121.553135692 ;
 397.073576593 ; 410.241832959 ; 434.118341756 ; 486.212542767 ; 656.386932735 ;
 1005.092490751 ; 1093.978221225 ; 1282.005727998 ; 1875,391236386 ; 2165.855872324 ;
 2625.547730940 ; 4051.771189722. (1,6)

However, substituting the new data (1.6) into the formula for the function $f(k)$, formula (1.1) gives identical results for the harmonic numbers of the individual waves: $\{H_n\} = 172800, 171500, 169344, 165375, 156800, 132300, 40500, 39200, 37044, 33075, 24500, 16000, 14700, 12544, 8575, 7425, 6125, 3969$.

The results represent exact harmonic numbers H_n , without rounding, retaining the highest degree of precision regardless of rounding and inaccuracies of the physical constants used .

Practical application of harmonic wave values:

If for the pair of orbits $\{n = 4, m = 5\}$ we get the formula: $H5 \setminus 4 = 3969$ [Hn]

where $H5 \setminus 4$ denotes the emission of a hydrogen atom when an electron jumps from orbit 5 to 4,

and: for the pair of orbits $\{n = 2, m = 7\}$ we get the formula: $H7 \setminus 2 = 40500$ [Hn]

where $H7 \setminus 2$ denotes the emission of a hydrogen atom when an electron jumps from orbit 7 to 2,

we can perform the calculation with full accuracy, without rounding:

$$\frac{\lambda (H7 \setminus 2) 40500}{\lambda (H5 \setminus 4) 3969} =$$

$$\text{so: } \lambda (H7 \setminus 2) = \lambda (H5 \setminus 4) * 40500 / 3969$$

where $\lambda (H5 \setminus 4)$ and $\lambda (H7 \setminus 2)$ denote the emission wavelength of a hydrogen atom when an electron jumps from orbit 5 to 4, and 7 to 2.

We can therefore calculate the length of another spectral line based on the wavelength of one spectral line.

To calculate all the values of λ_{and} hydrogen in [nm] units in full precision, without rounding, we lack one emission value in [nm], which will have the characteristics of a standard. Then all the other values calculated with the harmonic number calculation presented above would also become standard values, in full precision, without rounding.

Therefore, until such time as there is no standard, I propose describing the emission lines with harmonic numbers [Hn], which are unambiguous, precise, and described only by natural numbers.

Instead of the notation in [nm], where it is not possible to determine whether, for example, the lines 4051.771189722 [nm] and 4050.076359 [nm] are two different lines or the same line measured using two different methods.

λ_0 calculated by us using formula (1.2) for both of the above cases has the value :

$$\lambda_0 = k_{\text{min}} * \lambda_{\text{max}} = 3969 * 4051.771189722 \text{ [nm]} = 16081479.852008 \text{ [nm]}$$

$$\text{or } \lambda_0 = k_{\text{min}} * \lambda_{\text{max}} = 3969 * 4050.076359 \text{ [nm]} = 16074753.0693757 \text{ [nm]}$$

depending on the adopted wavelength standard λ (H5\4).

For further research I adopted a value from this range, which statistically best reflects the results of empirical measurements - $\lambda_0 = 16081464$ [nm]. A wave of this length will have a frequency $f_0 = 18.642112310$ [GHz], and the frequencies of all the hydrogen emission lines tested can be count as :

$$f (H5\4) = 18.642112310 \text{ [GHz]} * 3969 = 73,990.54375908 \text{ [GHz]}, \text{ or:}$$

$$f (H7\2) = 18.642112310 \text{ [GHz]} * 40500 = 755,005.54856200 \text{ [GHz]}.$$

I present a complete table of the spectral lines studied

λ_0	Harmonic number	λ_i	Frequency	f_0
16081464	* 172800	= 93.0640278	3221357,007	: 18.64211231 = 172800
16081464	* 171500	= 93.7694694	3197122,261	: 18.64211231 = 171500
16081464	* 169344	= 94.9632937	3156929,867	: 18.64211231 = 169344
16081464	* 165375	= 97.2424127	3082939,323	: 18.64211231 = 165375
16081464	* 156800	= 102.560357	2923083,21	: 18.64211231 = 156800
16081464	* 132300	= 121.553016	2466351,459	: 18.64211231 = 132300
16081464	* 40500	= 397.073185	755005,5486	: 18.64211231 = 40500
16081464	* 39200	= 410.241429	730770,8026	: 18.64211231 = 39200
16081464	* 37044	= 434.117914	690578,4084	: 18.64211231 = 37044
16081464	* 33075	= 486.212063	616587,8647	: 18.64211231 = 33075
16081464	* 24500	= 656.386286	456731.7516	: 18.64211231 = 24500
16081464	* 16000	= 1005.0915	298273,797	: 18.64211231 = 16000
16081464	* 14700	= 1093.97714	274039,051	: 18.64211231 = 14700
16081464	* 12544	= 1282.00446	233846.6568	: 18.64211231 = 12544
16081464	* 8575	= 1875.38939	159856,1131	: 18.64211231 = 8575
16081464	* 7425	= 2165.85374	138417,6839	: 18.64211231 = 7425
16081464	* 6125	= 2625.54514	114182.9379	: 18.64211231 = 6125
16081464	* 3969	= 4051.7672	73990,54376	: 18.64211231 = 3969

The table shows that the lambda wavelengths of all tested spectral lines are harmonics of the $\lambda_{0\text{ wave}}$ and the Harmonic number describes the number of full periods of the sinusoids of the individual waves in one period of the 16081464 nm wave. This also means that the frequencies of all the waves studied are discrete values with a modulus of 18.64211231 [GHz]. It can also be checked that the frequencies of all the waves studied are distant from all the others by an integer multiple of the modulus of 18.64211231 [GHz].

On this basis, one can put forward the thesis that all waves with subsequent harmonics N* 18.64211231 [GHz] for N = 1, 2, 3 can describe individual spectral lines that satisfy the condition described in the introduction.

We check whether the spectral lines of other elements also take values consistent with a discrete frequency grid with a modulus of **18.64211231 [GHz]**.

element	lambda measured	predicted lambda calculated from harmonic number
Rubidium (Rb)	420.178	420,1778 = 16081464 : 38273
Rhenium (Re)	396.232	396,2318 = 16081464 : 40586
Germanium (Ge)	288.861	288,8609 = 16081464 : 55672
Polonium (Po)	388.16	388,1599 = 16081464 : 41430
Rhodium (Rh)	343.489	343,4889 = 16081464 : 46818
Europium (Eu)	465.819	465,8188 = 16081464 : 34523
Germanium (Ge)	302.323	302,3229 = 16081464 : 53193
Polonium (Po)	405.78	405,7799 = 16081464 : 39631
Hafnium (Hf)	361.495	361,4949 = 16081464 : 44486
Sodium (Na)	589	588,9999 = 16081464 : 27303
Promethium (Pm)	428.759	428,759 = 16081464 : 37507
Argon (Ar)	706.722	706,7222 = 16081464 : 22755
Erbium (Er)	401.174	401,1741 = 16081464 : 40086
Gadolinium (Gd)	403.317	403,3171 = 16081464 : 39873
Iron G line (Fe)	432.518	432,5183 = 16081464 : 37181
Osmium (Os)	413.15	413,1503 = 16081464 : 38924
Neon (Ne)	585.248	585,2487 = 16081464 : 27478
Dysprosium (Dy)	380.608	380,6083 = 16081464 : 42252
Chromium (Cr)	425.435	425,4356 = 16081464 : 37800
Palladium (Pd)	340.485	340,4854 = 16081464 : 47231
Silver G line (Ag)	435.835	435,8357 = 16081464 : 36898
Mercury H line (Hg)	404.656	404,6568 = 16081464 : 39741
Calcium H line (Ca H)	396.847	396,8478 = 16081464 : 40523

I attempted to predict an unknown spectral line based on the calculated discrete values. I selected an undiscovered line $\lambda=371.2$ with energy 3.339 eV. The calculations show that this spectrum color can be obtained when transitioning from the 15th atomic orbit to the 2nd. Later I found a link to the NIST service and it turned out that there is a hydrogen line in the database at the transition from the 15th orbit to the 2nd and it is 371.19774.

Based on the algorithm, I predicted the existence of the line, which was later confirmed.

Most spectral lines on the NIST site are separated from each other by multiples of approximately 18.642 GHz.

It was also checked that the wavelengths on the NIST side⁵ of the elements coincide with the theoretically calculated discrete sites. These are the lines of: Au I 358.673 ; Au I 364.502 ; Au I 390.109 ; Au II 161.665 ; Au II 291.352 ; Au III 142.893 ; Ca III 197.8551 ; Ca III 212.6812 ; Ca III 532.1288 ; Ca III 799.357 ; Cr I 233.298 ; Cr I 236.513 ; Cr I 243.81 ; Cr I 289.824 ; Cr I 304.3714 ; Cr I 307.36743 ; Cr I 319.2287 ; Cr I 335.786 ; Cr I 336.552 ; Cr I 350.168 ; Cr I 350.3053 ; Cr II 117.54855 ; Cr II 123.67027 ; Cr II 123.67027 ; Cr II 144.58887 ; Cr II 148.13025 ; Cr II 150.73499 ; Cr II 151.2738 ; Cr II 163.41789 ; Cr II 168.08078 ; Cr II 170.0105 ; Cr II 172.0237 ; Cr II 179.76352 ; Cr II 182.5344 ; Cr II 182.5344 ; Cr II 183.99002 ; Cr II 208.91531 ; Cr II 211.8407 ; Cr II 224.997395 ; Cr II 230.6876 ; Cr II 232.52888 ; Cr II 235.3293 ; Cr II 244.70039 ; Cr II 245.08821 ; Cr II 245.40612 ; Cr II 246.57 635 ; Cr II 251.548 ; Cr II 251.91052 ; Cr II 253.69487 ; Cr II 255.57372 ; Cr II 259.30736 ; Cr II 260.49186 ; Cr II 262.97956 ; Cr II 264.2978 ; Cr II 265.20876 ; Cr II 267.98868 ; Cr II 268.50322 ; Cr II 270.8685 ; Cr II 273.95553 ; Cr II 281.046191 ; Cr II 281.08058 ; Cr II 288.9803 ; Cr II 297.479878 ; Cr II 313.44215 ; Cr IV 136.739 ; Cr V 104.6364 ; Cr V 120.4126 ; Cr V 157.9696 ; Dy I 421.124 ; Dy II 293.452 ; Dy II 332.619 ; Dy II 353.602 ; Er I 434.834 ; Er I 658.348 ; Er I 803.591 ; Er II 307.074 ; Er III 310.04 ; Eu I 306.6933 ; Eu I 563.254 ; Eu II 2 68.566 ; Eu II 295.947 ; Eu II 412.97 ; Eu II 417.516 ; Eu III 243.677 ; Eu III 302.34 ; Fe I 109.6603 ; Fe II 110.043 ; Fe II 120.7299 ; Fe II 121.8062 ; Fe II 128.5684 ; Fe II 132.0404 ; Fe II 132.8783 ; Fe II 132.8783 ; Fe II 133.041 ; Fe II 133.041 ; Fe II 133.041 ; Fe II 136.7297 ; Fe II 140.474 ; Fe II 141.5572 ; Fe II 142.7484 ; Fe II 144.3125 ; Fe II 146.1141 ; Fe II 148.7138 ; Fe II 149.3283 ; Fe II 149.45877 ; Fe II 151.914 ; Fe II 153.8631 ; Fe II 154.198 ; Fe II 156.4436 ; Fe II 158.9973 ; Fe II 165.6346 ; Fe II 165.6346 ; Fe II 166.60586 ; Fe II 184.431035 ; Fe II 188.1203 ; Fe II 188.36489 ; Fe III 91.73891 ; Fe III 92.7265 ; Fe III 96.3083 ; Fe III 96.3083 ; Fe III 100.9242 ; Fe III 101.37783 ; Fe III 103.1068 ; Fe III 106.3406 ; Fe III 107.0556 ; Fe III 110.5506 ; Fe III 111.6683 ; Fe III 115.8173 ; Fe III 123.83407 ; Fe III 126.0372 ; Fe III 129.1269 ; Fe III 131.9873 ; Fe III 138.0881 ; Fe III 138.4352 ; Fe III 139.3831 ; Fe III 146.21108 ; Fe III 156.13982 ; Fe III 156.8954 ; Fe III 159.3897 ; Fe III 166.1892 ; Fe III 1 73.7541 ; Fe III 175.2347 ; Fe III 184.3528 ; Fe III 184.3528 ; Fe III 184.6004 ; Fe III 187.8544 ; Fe IV 156.246 ; Fe IV 165.843 ; Fe V 93.7815 ; Fe V 93.8001 ; Fe V 97.6534 ; Fe V 101.4437 ; Fe V 136.5115 ; Fe V 137.3674 ; Fe V 139.4665 ; Fe V 140.2388 ; Fe V 140.2388 ; Fe V 140.7568 ; Fe V 140.8801 ; Fe V 145.6285 ; Fe V 156.3934 ; Fe V 165.4744 ; Ge I 1280.0655 ; Ge I 1466.752 ; Ge II 142.7877 ; Ge II 338.9782 ; Hf I 213.008 ; Hf I 214.471 ; Hf I 226.7582 ; Hf I 260.1842 ; Hf I 262.3318 ; Hf I 267.525 ; Hf I 280.2479 ; Hf I 306.3778 ; Hf I 307.0095 ; Hf I 319.8 ; Hf I 324.3735 ; Hf I 332.097 ; Hf I 340.9546 ; Hf I 340.9546 ; Hf I 350.6872 ; Hf I 382.264 ; Hf I 382.646 ; Hf I 386.091 ; Hf I 388.535 ; Hf I 391.267 ; Hf I 395.608 ; Hf I 404.779 ; Hf I 404.779 ; Hf I 430.446 ; Hf I 436.285 ; Hf I 449.09 ; Hf I 516.823 ; Hf I 538.526 ; Hf I 542.084 ; Hf I 545 .042 ; Hf I 548.612 ; Hf I 553.0268 ; Hf I 556.876 ; Hf I 560.115 ; Hf I 560.115 ; Hf I 601.536 ; Hf I 612.814 ; Hf I 623.651 ; Hf I 635.43 ; Hf I 652.39 2 ; Hf I 716.164 ; Hf I 718.1148 ; Hf I 728.558 ; Hf I 734.28 ; Hf I 744.719 ; Hf I 744.719 ; Hf I 755.637 ; Hf I 757.702 ; Hf I 778.952 ; Hf I 785.381 ; Hf I 786.726 ; Hf I 1093.382 ; Hf I 1161.2 ; Hf I 1161.2 ; Hf I 1202.173 ; Hf I 1833.9 ; Hf I 1861.28 ; Hf I 2141.91 ; Hf I 2314.88 ; Hf II 239.336 ; Hf II 251.548 ; Hf II 260.703 ; Hf II 289.871 ; Hf IV 201.406 ; On I 574.42 ; On II 155.7557 ; On II 157.5749 ; On II 201.9219 ; On II 301.151 ; On II 311.8134 ; On II 316.253 ; On II 317.27 ; On II 324.452 ; On II 438.7489 ; On II 443.847 ; On II 455.1787 ; On II 544.12 ; On III 156.287 ; On III 18 0.502 ; On III 193.0293 ; On III 217.3494 ; On III 218.2846 ; On III 723.12 ; On IV 159.57 ; On IV 161.857 ; On IV 197.43 ; On IV 640.9 ; On VI 175.6961 ; On VI 182.8 ; On VII 167.2 ; On VII 323.2 ; On VII 323.2 ; Ne I 294.90497 ; Ne I 295.7293 ; Ne I 295.7293 ; Ne I 388.7134 ; Ne I 440.29 85 ; Ne I 451.017 ; Ne I 503.60016 ; Ne I 585.24878 ; Ne I 889.56 ; Ne I 1691.0058 ; Ne I 1731.051 ; Ne I 2967.6059 ; Ne I 4042.5964 ; Ne I 5116 .59 ; Ne II 157.875 ; Ne II 175.1698 ; Ne II 200.18752 ; Ne II 293.527 ; Ne II 299.4909 ; Ne II 321.1989 ; Ne II 332.715344 ; Ne II 336.05 97 ; Ne II 340.694511 ; Ne II 357.461224 ; Ne II 432.2742 ; Ne II 1032.717 ; Ne II 1136.57982 ; Ne II 1681.106 ; Ne II 1741.5492 ; Ne II 481 0.493 ; Ne III 130.613 ; Ne III 130.8468 ; Ne III 157.3806 ; Ne IV 106.316 ; Ne IV 122.3353 ; Ne VI 91.29 ; Ne VI 225.3 ; Ne VII 251.32 ; Ne VII 255.72 ; Ne VII 450.6 ; Ne VIII 137.29 ; Pm I 332.922 ; Pm I 460.985 ; Pm I 485.273 ; Pm I 670.033 ; Pm II 348.061 ; After I 332.86 ; After I 38 6.193 ; Rb I 358.705 ; Rb I 519.52778 ; Rb II 180.2976 ; Rb II 249.8402 ; Rb II 306.7752 ; Rb II 323.4666 ; Rb II 884.5203 ; Rb III 309.8488 ; Rb III 334.4661 ; Rb IV 144.9917 ; Rb IV 170.776 ; Rb IV 278.9451 ; Re I 235.65 ; Re I 240.072 ; Re III 112.16913 ; Re III 124.09112 ; Re III 12 6.04609 ; Re III 126.92052 ; Re III 128.43286 ; Re III 158.34914 ; Re III 162.11154 ; Re III 162.30296 ; Re III 167.11835 ; Re III 187.04378 ; Re III 197.74804 ; Re III 198.65432 ; Re III 198.91232 ; Re IV 93.83896 ; Re IV 97.60006 ; Re IV 97.62139 ; Re IV 142.07746 ; Re IV 153.08245 ; Re IV 155.4125 ; Re IV 202.22661 ; Rh I 232.173 ; Rh II 247.754 ; Sat I 178.824 ; Sat I 323.252 ; Sat I 338.315 ; Sat III 171.023 ; Sat III 261.717 [nm].

⁵<https://physics.nist.gov>

Chapter 2

In the first chapter I proposed using a new wave unit "Harmonic number" [Hn] instead of the unit [cm⁻¹]. Unlike cm⁻¹ it describes each spectral line uniquely without rounding.

However, in order to calculate the energy value in [Hn] without rounding, a formula must be created to go directly from the orbit number to this unit, omitting the rounded physical constants.

Similarly to Rydberg, I calculate the proportionality factor "M" which calculates the energy of the emission wave in units [Hn]

$$E [Hn] = M * (1/m^2 - 1/n^2) \quad (2.1)$$

E[Hn] - emission wave energy in [Hn] units

M – proportionality factor

m, n – orbit numbers

For the next 21 emission cases, the Harmonic number is calculated as the integer form of the quotient λ_0 and λ_i (16081464 [nm] / λ_i)

Lambda Hydrogen	low orbit m	high orbit n	Harmonic number [Hn]	$1/m^2 - 1/n^2$	M = Hn / $1/m^2 - 1/n^2$
4052.269	4	5	3969	0.0225	176400
4376.458	6	12	3675	0.020833333	176400
4653.774	5	7	3456	0.019591837	176400
5091.321	7	20	3159	0.017908163	176400
5128.662	6	10	3136	0.017777778	176400
5711.464	7	15	2816	0.015963719	176400
5956.845	7	14	2700	0.015306122	176400
6771.993	7	12	2375	0.013463719	176400
7459.84	5	6	2156	0.012222222	176400
8760.068	7	10	1836	0.010408163	176400
12156.83	10	20	1323	0.0075	176400
12371.91	6	7	1300	0.007369615	176400
16411.71	10	15	980	0.005555556	176400
18615.14	10	14	864	0.004897959	176400
20514.64	12	20	784	0.004444444	176400
29839.49	10	12	539	0.003055556	176400
35040.27	14	20	459	0.002602041	176400
36470.46	12	15	441	0.0025	176400
46890.6	15	20	343	0.001944444	176400
49487.6	12	14	325	0.001842404	176400
138651	14	15	116	0.000657596	176400

We will calculate the first case algebraically:

$$M * (1/4^2 - 1/5^2) = 3969 \quad (2.2)$$

$$M = 3969 / (0.0625 - 0.04) = 3969 / 0.0225 = \mathbf{176400} \quad (2.3)$$

From the table it follows that the proportionality coefficient is exactly the number 176400. For further research we will use this number in the prime number decomposition:

$$\mathbf{176400 = 2^4 \times 3^2 \times 5^2 \times 7^2} \quad (2.4)$$

For the purpose of continuing the calculations we must suspend the validity of Bohr's P4 postulate of the equality of orbital energies (orbital energy difference) and

photon energy. We will use the description E_o as orbital energy and E_f as photon energy, without assuming a priori that they are equal.

For all hydrogen lines with integer orbit numbers, I created a balance of the conversion of orbit energy into photon emission energy, for example:

$$\text{Energy of orbits (energy difference of orbits) } E_o [\text{Hn}] = M * (1/m^2 - 1/n^2)$$

$$\text{Energy of the produced photon } E_f = \text{INTEGER}(\lambda_o / \lambda_i) = \text{INTEGER}(16081464 [\text{nm}] / \lambda_i)$$

For the case of an electron jumping from orbit 5 to 4 we get:

$$E_o = 176400 * 0.0225 = 3969 [\text{Hn}]$$

$$E_f = \text{Integer} (16081464 / 4052.269) = 3969 [\text{Hn}]$$

$$E_o - E_f = 3969 - 3969 = 0$$

These energies, as Bohr assumed, are equal; the energy balance of the orbital energy loss minus the photon energy gain is equal to zero and postulate P4 is fulfilled, but this is not a universal principle.

Below is the balance graph in the 90 nm – 80000 nm band

We are surprised to find that the energy balance is almost zero for about 100 of the lines studied, while there are cases where the difference is 20 energy units [Hn] - that is about $20 * 7.71 * 10^{-5}$ [eV].

In addition, the shape of the graph allows us to assume that the differences are not the result of random calculation errors, but are systemic, resulting from an as yet unknown relationship.

After conducting thorough analytical studies of the balance sheet results, the methods of which I will not cite in this work, I concluded that:

However, careful broadband analysis has shown that for some combinations of starting and final orbits an energy match does exist.

These are only orbits with numbers 40, 35, 30, 28, 21, 20, 15, 14, 12, 10, 7, 6, 5, 4 and all their combinations obey Bohr's P4 postulate. (2.5)

For the remaining orbit combinations, from the set {1, 2, 3, 8, 9, 11, 13, 16, 17, 18, 19, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 29, 31, 32, 33, 34, 36, 37, 38, 39} I created an algorithm that maps the energy difference into a numerical value, which I called the "Event Marker".

$$\text{Marker} = 176400 \cdot (B^2 - A^2) - \text{INTEGER}(16081464 / \lambda) \quad (2.6)$$

where A - higher orbit number
 B - lower orbit number
 λ - measured hydrogen wavelength [nm]

From the physical point of view, the "Marker" is a determinant of the difference between the energy lost by the orbits and the energy gained by the photon, it is counted in units of approximately $7.71 \cdot 10^{-5}$, and for all combinations of orbit numbers mentioned in (2.5) it should take the value "0".

This marker is a combination of two values characteristic for the starting and final orbit. The Orbit Marker values characterize a given orbit in an unambiguous way and have an accuracy of millionths of a decimal place.

For example: For the emission from orbit 18 to 9 the measured value $\lambda = 9847.025$

$$\text{Marker } 18 > 9 = 176400 \cdot (9^2 - 18^2) - \text{INTEGER}(16081464 / 9847,025) = 0.333333333333(3)$$

The orbit marker 18 is 0.555555555(5) and the orbit marker 9 is 0.222222222(2) – see table (2.8).

We can create a universal equation:

$$\text{Higher orbit marker} - \text{Lower orbit marker} = \text{Event marker} \quad (2.7)$$

Below are the values of some of the orbit markers 1 – 40: (2.8)

40	0,75	29	0,249702735	17	-0,380622837
39	0,023668639	27	0,024691358	16	-0,0625
38	0,83933518	26	0,053254438	13	0,213017751
37	0,146822498	25	0,76	11	0,148760331
36	0,888888889	24	0,75	9	0,222222222
34	0,404844291	23	0,540642722	8	-0,25
33	0,016528926	22	0,537190083	3	3
32	0,734375	19	0,35734072	2	7
31	0,441207076	18	0,555555556	1	-20

Of course, we can also count smaller jumps and in reverse order:

Example: For the emission from orbit 18 to 13 the measured emission value $\lambda = 32209.32$

The orbit marker 18 is 0.555555555(5) and the orbit marker 13 is 0.21301

From this it follows that the Event Marker 18>13 will be equal to

$$0.55555 - 0.21301 = 0.342537747$$

we check:

$$\text{Marker } 18 > 13 = 176400 \cdot (13^{-2} - 18^{-2}) - \text{INTEGER}(16081464/32209.32) = 0.342537$$

Example: We can calculate the parameters of the second jump to orbit 9, when the intermediate orbit 13, previously the final one, turns into the initial orbit:

For the emission from orbit 13 to 9 the measured emission value $\lambda = 14183.07$

The orbit marker 13 is 0.21301 and the orbit marker 9 is 0.222222222

From this it follows that the Event Marker 13>9 will be equal to -0.0092.

we check:

$$\text{Marker } 13 > 9 = 176400 \cdot (9^{-2} - 13^{-2}) - \text{INTEGER}(16081464/14183.07) = -0.0092044707$$

Additionally, adding both jumps 18>13 and 13>9 we get the equality:

$$0.342537 + (-0.0092044707) = 0.333333333$$

which is exactly what the 18>9 marker was at the beginning

Example: We can also calculate the inverse problem:

Task to solve: Someone calculated that the event marker was -0.2112603306, what kind of event was it?

Solution: Marker A - Marker B = -0.2112603306

This marker value can only be composed of table values

$$-0.0625 - 0.148760331 = -0.2112603306$$

The values that satisfy the equation are orbit markers 16 and 11.

Example: An easier task is when we ask about one of the orbits with marker value =0, e.g. 40, 35, 30, 28, 21, 20, 15, 14, 12, 10, 7, 6, 5, 4. For the jump between orbits 20 and 11 we use the same formula:

Higher orbit marker - Lower orbit marker = Event marker

$$0 - 0.148760331 = -0.148760331$$

we check:

$$\text{Marker } 20 > 11 = 176400 \cdot (11^{-2} - 20^{-2}) - \text{INTEGER}(16081464/15816.95) = -0.1487603306$$

and vice versa, i.e. to the orbit with the zero marker 19 > 7 :

$$\text{Upper Orbit Marker } 19 - \text{Lower Orbit Marker } 7 = \text{Event Marker } 19 > 7$$

we check: Marker $19 > 7 = 0.357341 - 0 = 0.357341$

$176400 \cdot (7^{-2} - 19^{-2}) - \text{INTEGER}(16081464/5169, 282) = 0.3573407202$

As I mentioned at the beginning. Only for orbits from the group 40, 35, 30, 28, 21, 20, 15, 14, 12, 10, 7, 6, 5, 4 we do not take into account any corrections.

What do markers give us? In addition to easy recognition of the orbit numbers to which they are assigned, they also have some physical meaning for the atom, but this may be the subject of further research.

The markers are very precise, with virtually no error. However, then the table of orbit markers must be given as a fraction of powers of natural numbers.

Conclusion: In all studied cases the difference between the energy of the orbits and the energy of the emitted photon is systematic and consists in the application of two corrections - one integrally related to the initial orbit number and the other related to the final orbit number.

The energy of the event calculated using Bohr's formulas must be corrected (except for cases with marker = 0) by the value of the marker of the higher orbit and the lower orbit. Then the agreement between the difference in orbit energy and the photon energy is perfect.

Chapter 3

Calculations

The exact value of the energy of the basic level (fundamental state) of the hydrogen atom E_0 , calculated according to the Bohr model, is:

Energy is expressed by the formula:

$$E_n = -\frac{m_e e^4}{8\epsilon_0^2 h^2 n^2},$$

Where:

m_e : electron mass $\approx 9.10938356 \times 10^{-31}$ kg,

e : electron charge $\approx 1.602176634 \times 10^{-19}$ C,

ϵ_0 : electric permittivity of vacuum $8.8541878128 \times 10^{-12}$ F/m,

h : Planck's constant $\approx 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34}$ Js

n : principal quantum number (for ground state $n=1$).

$$\text{For } n=1 \text{ } E_0=2.179872 * 10^{-18} \text{ J} = \underline{\underline{13.60569 \text{ eV}}}$$

The commonly used encyclopedia value is 13.6 eV.

We construct the conversion factor between the [Hn] unit and the [eV] unit Hn/eV:

Example:

A hydrogen atom, when an electron moves from orbit 15 to orbit 12, emits a wavelength of 36470.46 nm

Harmonic number (Harmonic number = INTEGER (16081464/36470.46) = 441 [Hn] – this is the photon emission energy in [Hn] units

You can also count: $176400 * (12^{-1} - 15^{-1}) = 176400 * 0.0025 = 441$ - this is the energy lost by the orbits.

Having two energy values E0 at our disposal, we obtain the conversion factors:

$$H_n/E_1 = 441 * 13.60569 = 6000.10929$$

$$H_n/E_2 = 441 * 13.6 = 5999.60000$$

For the calculations I used the intermediate value = 6000.0

The energy E0 for the assumed value of the product is: $6000/441 = \underline{\underline{13.6054421768707 \text{ eV}}}$

This is a rounded value, the exact value calculated without loss is

$$6000/441 = 2^4 * 3 * 5^3 / 3^2 * 7^2 = \underline{\underline{2000/147 \text{ eV}}}$$

I calculate energy conversions Hn to eV

For the emission of an electron from orbit 5 to 4 we write the energy equality:

$$E_0 (1/4^2 - 1/5^2) \text{ eV} = 3969 \text{ [Hn]}$$

$$2000/147 (1/16 - 1/25) = 3^3 * 3^3 * 7^7 \text{ [Hn]}$$

We get the conversion factor:

$$\underline{\underline{1 \text{ [Hn]} = 2^2 * 2^2 * 5^5 * 5 (9/16 * 25) / 3^7 * 7^3 * 3^3 * 3^3 * 7^7 = 5 / (3^3 * 7^4) \text{ [eV]}}}$$

We calculate the electron emission energy losslessly by substituting the conversion factor value:

$$\text{For the emission of an electron from orbit 5 to 4 the energy is } 3969 \text{ [Hn]} = (3969 * (5/3^3 * 7^4) \text{ eV} = 3^4 * 7^2 * 5 / (3^3 * 7^4) = 5^3/7^2 = \underline{\underline{15/49 \text{ eV}}}$$

The rounded value of this energy (loss) will be **0.306122449 eV**

Below is a table. Some lossless emission values of the hydrogen atom:

orbit high	orbit low	algorithm	energy e.V.
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5	4	$3 \cdot 5 / (7^2)$	15/49
6	5	$2^2 \cdot 11 \cdot 5 / (3^3 \cdot 7^2)$	220/1323
7	5	$2^7 \cdot 5 / (7^4)$	640/2401
7	6	$2^2 \cdot 5^3 \cdot 13 / (3^4 \cdot 7^4)$	6500/64827
10	6	$2^6 \cdot 5 / (3^3 \cdot 7^2)$	320/1323
10	7	$2^2 \cdot 17 \cdot 5 / (7^4)$	340/2401
12	6	$5^3 / (3^2 \cdot 7^2)$	125/441
12	7	$5^4 \cdot 19 / (3^3 \cdot 7^4)$	11875/64827
12	10	$11 \cdot 5 / (3^3 \cdot 7^2)$	55/1323
14	7	$2^2 \cdot 5^3 / (7^4)$	500/2401
14	10	$2^5 \cdot 5 / (7^4)$	160/2401
14	12	$5^3 \cdot 13 / (3^3 \cdot 7^4)$	1625/64827
15	7	$2^8 \cdot 11 \cdot 5 / (3^3 \cdot 7^4)$	14080/64827
15	10	$2^2 \cdot 5^2 / (3^3 \cdot 7^2)$	100/1323
15	12	$5 / (3 \cdot 7^2)$	5/147
15	14	$2^4 \cdot 29 \cdot 5 / (3^3 \cdot 7^4)$	580/64827
20	7	$3^2 \cdot 13 \cdot 5 / (7^4)$	585/2401
20	10	$5 / (7^2)$	5/49
20	12	$2^4 \cdot 5 / (3^3 \cdot 7^2)$	80/1323
20	14	$17 \cdot 5 / (7^4)$	85/2401
20	15	$5 / (3^3 \cdot 7)$	5/189